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Public Attitudes Toward Tax Evasion and Redistribution: Evidence from Five Euro-Asian Countries

KEYWORDS

tax evasion attitudes,
Euro-Asian countries,
World Values Survey,
taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor,
demographic variables (gender and age)
comparative analysis

ABSTRACT

This study explored two public finance questions – attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion, and whether it is a legitimate function of government to tax the rich and subsidize the poor. It also compared the relative quality of three artificial intelligence chat bots – Microsoft Copilot, Google Gemini and DeepSeek. The three chat bots were asked to list countries that are both in Europe and Asia. They all listed the same five countries – Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Russia and Turkey. One of the bots merely listed the countries and gave a few additional words, while the other two bots volunteered additional information. The bots were then asked to summarize the views toward the justifiability of tax evasion in each country, and to provide citations to the sources they used to arrive at their conclusion. The length of their responses varied somewhat. All of their replies provided good summaries and were grammatically correct. The sources listed were different in each case.

The World Values Survey data for the five countries was then examined on the issue of the justifiability of tax evasion to determine the relative overall views of each country. Additional comparisons were made of gender views and views by age to determine if either demographic variable was significant. There were significant differences in some cases.

Another World Values Survey question examined the issue of whether taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor constituted an essential characteristic of democracy in the minds of the people in those five Euro-Asian countries. An overall comparison was made for the five countries. Additional comparisons were also made by gender and age to learn whether any differences in these two demographic variables were significant.

This study makes several contributions to the literature. Although attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion has been studied numerous times, the present study is the first to compare attitudes in the five Euro-Asian countries on this issue. Likewise, although a few studies have been made on the idea that taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor should or should not be an essential characteristic of a democracy, this study is the first to examine and compare the views of the people in the five Euro-Asian countries. The present study is one of the few to compare the relative quality of chat bots and is perhaps the first to make a comparison of Microsoft Copilot, Google Gemini and DeepSeek. The conclusions are that all three chat bots performed well, although it would be a subjective judgment on the part of the author to determine which chat bot did the best or worst job of responding to the instructions; an examination of the two tax questions that were included in the World Values Survey database determined that there were some significant differences between the views of the five countries both for attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion and for the view that taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor constituted an essential function of a democracy. Some differences based on gender and age were also found.

FOR CITATION

Received: Dec 9, 2025
Accepted: Mar 12, 2026
Published: Jun 1, 2026

McGee, R. W., Geyik, O., & Benk, S. (2026). Public Attitudes Toward Tax Evasion and Redistribution: Evidence from Five Euro-Asian Countries. *Economic Consultant*, (2), 83–101. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2026.2.5>

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the research topic stems from the fact that tax evasion reduces government revenues, increases the redistribution of the tax burden onto law-abiding taxpayers, and undermines the effectiveness of financing public goods (education, healthcare, infrastructure). The study of attitudes toward tax evasion addresses key questions about how public perception and trust in the state influence real compliance decisions with tax laws, and what policies the state can implement to raise tax compliance without undermining trust and legitimacy.

D. Falsetta & B. C. Spilker studied how the inefficiency of tax administration services, manifested in delays in processing paper-filed tax returns, indirectly affects taxpayers' intentions to evade taxes through taxpayers' psychological reactions to the delay. The authors found that when taxpayers experience a delay in tax refunds, they experience psychological reactance (for example, anger and frustration with the tax administration), which amplifies their intentions to evade taxes [1].

M. Mutascu investigates the interaction between tax evasion and bribery, emphasizing the trade-off between penalties for evasion and the deterring effect of sanctions for bribery. The article introduces a new concept of the "paradox of tax evasion and bribery." The author stresses that a higher probability of detecting bribery significantly reduces its actual occurrence. In this framework, the level of tax evasion is bounded by the tax rate, while the imposition of evasion penalties induces bribery [2].

I. A. Ergashev argues that tax law does not merely regulate behavior—it actively constructs the very category of the "financial citizen" through semiotic processes that shape individuals' understanding of their relationship with the state. The author proposes a "Semiotic Model of Compliance," which integrates sign theory with existing behavioral models, offering both theoretical insights and practical recommendations for tax policy design [3].

D. T. Tumoro & H. B. Pandya show that taxpayers' attitudes, justice and honesty, as well as taxpayers' culture, have a statistically significant direct positive influence on both government tax revenues and taxpayers' behavior regarding compliance with tax legislation. However, the study did not find a statistically significant direct link between tax education and tax revenues, nor between tax education and taxpayers' behavior regarding compliance with tax legislation [4].

Y. Sun & L. Song show that establishing regional branches of the State Tax Administration significantly reduces tax evasion. The mechanism of this reduction lies in enhanced tax activity by local tax authorities and the curbing of abuses by related-party entities within companies [5].

B. Torgler analyzes tax morale as a dependent variable, which allows addressing questions about the factors that shape it. By combining data from Asian countries, the author found, for example, that trust in government and the legal system has a positive influence on tax morale [6].

C. Hoy et al. examine the prevalence of tax evasion among firms in Indonesia. According to researchers, about a quarter of firms evade taxes. Firms that consider the tax administration a serious obstacle to their business are more likely to evade taxes [7].

E. Appiah et al. established that democracy significantly increases tax revenues, while corruption hinders their growth. Moreover, the quality of bureaucracy and democracy are complementary factors influencing tax revenues, whereas corruption and the quality of bureaucracy are substitutable factors reducing tax revenues in Africa [8].

Thus, the effectiveness of tax policy depends not only on laws and penalties but also on the quality of administration, trust in the state, perceptions of justice, and cultural factors. Information-social mechanisms (delays, communication, regional structures, level of bureaucracy) influence taxpayers' behavior and overall tax collection.

Aim of the article: to determine and compare the relationship between the public's attitude toward tax evasion and the attitude toward the redistribution of tax revenues, using data from five Euro-Asian countries, identifying common patterns and regional differences within the context of culturally and institutionally diverse conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials. Articles from peer-reviewed journals were used, including the *Journal of Accounting, Ethics & Public Policy*; *International Journal of Social Economics*; *African Journal of Business Management*; *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*; and others. Conference materials and papers were used, in particular the paper presented at the 35th International Public Finance Conference.

Monographs and books used included *Taxes and Trust* (Cambridge University Press); *A General Theory of Crime* (Stanford University Press); *The Ethics of Redistribution*; *Two Treatises of Government*; *The Ethics of Tax Evasion: Perspectives in Theory and Practice*, and others.

Methods. The study employed a five-country survey: Turkey, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, and Russia. Measurement: a 10-point Likert scale was used (1 = never justifiable, 10 = always justifiable). The primary dependent variable was the assessment of the justifiability of tax evasion. Additional analysis groups included gender (male/female) and age (age groups). Descriptive statistics for each country are provided using the mean and standard deviation. Welch's unpaired t-test was used to compare means between countries.

RESULTS

1 The Tax Evasion Literature

The study analyzing the tax culture in Georgia shows that the success of tax reforms is not always clear in these countries [9]. In another study, the ability to pay taxes, correct tax payment, increasing citizens' tax morale and awareness, and reassessment of deterrent policies (such as exemptions, audits, fines and penalties) were perceived as factors contributing to compliance behavior among taxpayers [10]. Finally, a study in Georgia conducted a broad, multi-methodological and socio-economic evaluation of Georgia's tax lottery experience in 2012. The study found that those who reported their income and average weekly sales were higher during the lottery weeks [11].

The study conducted in Azerbaijan examined the importance of tax ethics and the impact of education on tax ethics. As a result of the empirical research, it was revealed that the attitude towards tax compliance was higher after passing tax courses [12].

Studies on this subject in Turkey can be summarized as follows: In the study examining the historical development of the Turkish Revenue Administration, 2005 represents an important turning point in terms of radical changes in the organizational structure and working method. The transformation to a flexible and agile structure shifted the focus to taxpayers and enabled fast and effective decisions to be made [13]. Another study examined how various demographic differences affect tax perception during the COVID-19 pandemic [14]. The tax compliance behaviors

of independent accounting professionals were examined. It was determined that trust in the government has a positive and statistically significant relationship on the perception of tax justice [15]. The study examined tax participation, tax evasion, welfare and life satisfaction [16]. A study was conducted to investigate Turkish taxpayers' perceptions of the seriousness of tax evasion compared to other crimes and violations. The results of the study show that tax evasion ranked 10th among the 21 crimes surveyed [17]. The study found that religiosity has a significant effect on voluntary tax compliance [18].

In another study conducted for Turkey, it was found that power and trust have an effect on mandatory tax compliance and voluntary compliance. A study was conducted to investigate whether there are dimensions of tax justice in Turkey. As a result of the research, it was concluded that there are dimensions of tax justice [19]. With the questionnaire prepared using national and international scales, cognitive, affective and psychomotor dimensions, sub-dimensions of tax literacy, trust and fairness, tax compliance and non-compliance factors were analyzed. It was concluded that the cognitive dimension was effective in determining the level of tax literacy of tax educated people, while the emotional dimension remained in the background [20]. In another study conducted for Turkey. After receiving tax awareness training, it was determined that children's views on taxes changed and they were more aware of the reasons for tax collection. Policy recommendations were made in the context of the findings of the study [21].

In another study, it was concluded that social expenditures would decrease due to tax evasion and this would negatively affect welfare [22]. In another study on this subject, it was concluded that tax education has positive effects on children's tax awareness [23]. In another important study on this subject, the findings show that social capital variables and some demographic factors have significant effects on tax morality in Turkey. Trust variables have a positive effect on tax morality; taxpayers are willing to pay taxes if they trust political entities. Religion and national pride have a positive effect on tax morality [24]. In another study, tax morality was defined as the intrinsic motivation to pay taxes voluntarily and it was concluded that it is influenced by many factors such as education, demographic, economic or socio-cultural background of individuals [25]. In another study, in terms of tax evasion and financial crimes, the legal dimension of the sanctions applied to this crime was evaluated within the framework of the Turkish Tax System [26]. Using an econometric analysis, the study found that high tax morality is significantly more likely when there is trust in government (normative dimension), a sense of belonging

to the nation (cultural-cognitive dimension), and perceptions of penalty risk and severity (regulatory-instrumental dimension) [27].

Another study showed that although religiosity seems to be an influential factor in tax compliance behavior, it may seem irrelevant under certain conditions [28]. In another Turkish study, it was concluded that economic criteria affected tax ethics the most, followed by political, psychological and sociological criteria, with social capital coming in as the least affective criteria [29]. Finally, in the study conducted on this subject; it was concluded that the marital status factor was effective on attitudes and behaviors towards taxes. On the other hand, various differences were found in the attitudes and behaviors of taxpayers towards taxes in terms of education level [23].

It is possible to summarize the studies conducted in Russia on this issue as follows. One study examined citizens' attitudes towards paying taxes by focusing on the experiences of individuals in the Russian Federation. The study concluded that tax evasion and the perception of a corrupt and inefficient state are consistent with the importance of social norms in tax compliance, where tax evasion and the perception of a corrupt and inefficient state initially leads to a decline in tax morality [30]. In another study, the components of tax evasion were comprehensively examined [31]. In another study, a Logit analysis of tax compliance attitudes was conducted using taxpayer compliance attitude surveys in countries including Russia [32]. Another study analyzed the effects of Russia's 2001 flat-rate income tax reform on consumption, income and tax evasion using micro-level data [33].

Another Russian study analyzed tax evasion patterns in various segments of the forestry industry and examined the impact of the size of enterprises and the level of tax audit risk on the frequency of the same type of tax responses [34]. Another study examined Russian managers' perceptions of the relationship between legal and ethical behavior. The research results show that managers believe that under the current conditions in Russia, businesses cannot perform in a completely legal way. Therefore, illegal performance is seen as legitimate and ethical [35]. Another study explained the main links between formal rules and informal practices in the Russian economy [36]. In a different study, economic models of federalism often emphasize the beneficial effects of competition between regions to attract mobile voters or capital. This paper identifies two less benign aspects of such competition [37]. The paper addresses the problem of determining the optimal taxation for the individual. Since a taxpayer's income is private information, it can only be verified through a costly audit [38]. Finally, this study deals with Russia's "black money" economy. We

examine the mechanics of tax evasion in Russia and provide a rough estimate of the scale and dynamics involved in tax evasion based on black money [39].

2 Taxing the Rich & Subsidizing the Poor

Taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor is considered a typical financial feature of democracy and a solution to reduce income inequality. Whether reducing income inequality by the use of the tax system is ethically acceptable is a controversial issue that we will leave for another day. The purpose of the present study is merely to determine the extent of support for this policy approach to reducing income inequality.

The rich have to pay more, while the poor can enjoy “free” income. Some studies have found that the democratic act of 'taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor' actually reduces financial satisfaction [40]. Recent studies on the ethical justification of unequal tax rates offer contrasting views. A number of studies have assessed the ethical foundations of discriminatory tax systems. Some of these studies conclude that there is no clear moral justification for imposing different prices on different individuals [41].

Another study first outlines policy options for raising large amounts of revenue from the richest, first discussing potential incremental reforms and then focusing on four main options for more structural reforms: (1) significantly increasing top tax rates on labor and other ordinary income, (2) taxing the rich on gains as they arise and accrue at ordinary rates, (3) a wealth tax on high net income individuals, and (4) a financial transaction tax. While these approaches have relative advantages and disadvantages, it is argued that they should be considered [42].

It examines the aggregate and distributional effects of increasing the top marginal income tax rate on tax evasion. It is argued that eliminating tax avoidance by giving entrepreneurs equal tax treatment across all legal forms of business organization would significantly increase tax revenue, aggregate output and welfare [43]. It is argued that wealth tax increases targeting the wealthy may accelerate their migration to regions with lower taxes. While regional tax increases at the municipal scale may increase local mobility, they will not cause a significant change on national movement [44]. Similarly, it is stated that as a result of excessive taxation of the rich, these people will move to countries with lower tax rates, thus causing wealth migration [45]. A question in the latest World Values Survey explored whether it is a fundamental feature of democratic governments to tax the rich and subsidize

the poor. A trend analysis was also conducted to determine whether German views have changed over time [46; 47]. In another study, the World Values Survey reports the findings of a survey conducted by scientists in 60 countries on the question of whether governments should tax the rich and subsidize the poor. The results varied widely depending on the country [48]. A study was conducted in the United States using the World Values Survey on the question of whether governments should tax the rich and subsidize the poor [49]. Another study analyzed Internal Revenue Service data and applied philosophical and ethical concepts in trying to determine whether the rich pay their fair share of income taxes [50]. Another study used the latest World Values Survey (WVS) dataset to determine whether Christian and Muslim views on the acceptability of taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor are a fundamental feature of democracy. The study concluded that differences in perspective are generally significant [47; 48]. In another study, a question in the latest World Values Survey presents the findings of a survey conducted in South Korea on whether democratic governments should tax the rich and subsidize the poor. It is discussed along with findings on specific demographic variables such as gender and age [51]. Finally, another recent study aimed to test the relationship between trust in public programs and distributive justice in taxation on a nationwide basis [52].

Some studies have been made of attitudes toward tax evasion in Azerbaijan [53], Georgia [54; 55], Kazakhstan [56; 57], Russia [58; 59] and Turkey [16; 19]. The present study aims to replicate and update the findings of those studies.

Only a few studies have been done that focus on the question of whether it is an essential function of democracy to tax the rich and subsidize the poor. Studies have been conducted that examine views in South Korea [51] and Germany [60]. A comparative study was done of Christian and Muslim views [47]. That's not many studies. It is an area that is ripe for more studies.

EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

The first step was to determine which countries to include in this study. We wanted to include countries that were in both Europe and Asia. We decided to ask three artificial intelligence assistants – Microsoft Copilot, Google Gemini and DeepSeek – to see if they reached a consensus. They did. They all listed the same five countries – Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Russia and Turkey. They also all gave some additional information about each country. Microsoft Copilot volunteered the least additional, unsolicited information. Gemini and DeepSeek gave a little more

information. We then asked them to provide some information about the attitude toward the acceptability of tax evasion in each country, and to provide references. They all gave some basic information, along with references. The references each AI assistant gave were different. The references DeepSeek gave were not very accurate, the excuse being that it did not have the ability to search databases.

The next step was to retrieve the data needed for the present study. Every five years or so a large group of scholars surveys many people in many countries, asking many questions about many subjects. These scholars are part of the World Values Survey [61]. In the most recent wave (Wave 7, 2017–2022) they surveyed more than 150,000 people in more than 90 countries on a wide range of issues. The most recent survey included two questions about taxation. One question asked whether tax evasion could ever be justifiable. The other question asked whether taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor is an essential characteristic of democracy. The present study explores the views of those surveyed in five Euro-Asian countries: Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Russia and Turkey.

How Justifiable Is Tax Evasion?

One tax question asked whether cheating on taxes if you had a chance could ever be justified. The survey instrument used a 10-point Likert scale, where 1 = never justifiable and 10 = always justifiable. The results are presented in Table 1. Turkey showed the strongest opposition to tax evasion. Russia showed the least opposition.

Overall

Table 1

Overall Ranking (1 = never justifiable; 10 = always justifiable)

Rank	Country	Mean	Std. Dev.	n
1	Turkey	1.69	1.64	2395
2	Georgia	2.23	2.14	2190
3	Kazakhstan	2.95	2.50	1212
4	Azerbaijan	2.99	2.70	1728
5	Russia	3.76	2.86	3513

Table 2 shows the tests of significance. The Welch's unpaired t-test was used to calculate significance because various mathematicians have determined that it is somewhat superior to the student t-test [62; 63]. In almost all comparisons, the difference in mean scores was highly significant. The only comparison that showed similar views was the Kazakhstan-Azerbaijan comparison.

Table 2Tests of Significance (Significant if $p < 0.05$)

Country	Georgia	Kazakhstan	Azerbaijan	Russia
Turkey	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Georgia		<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Kazakhstan			0.6836	<0.0001
Azerbaijan				<0.0001

Gender

Table 3 shows the gender views. In all cases the male and female groups had views that were not significantly different.

Table 3

Gender Differences

Country	Male			Female			p-value
	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	
Azerbaijan	2.99	2.66	882	2.98	2.74	846	0.9387
Georgia	2.23	2.19	1008	2.23	2.09	1182	1.0000
Kazakhstan	3.00	2.52	546	2.90	2.49	666	0.4897
Russia	3.77	2.84	1605	3.75	2.87	1908	0.8639
Turkey	1.68	1.64	1200	1.69	1.64	1195	0.8814

Age

Comparisons were also made by age. Table 4 shows the statistics for each country. Three countries – Azerbaijan, Georgia and Turkey – had hyperbolic functions where the mean score first increased, then decreased. In these three cases a p-value was calculated comparing the high and low mean scores. The difference was significant for Azerbaijan ($p = 0.0370$) but not for Georgia ($p = 0.4888$) and Turkey ($p = 0.5428$). The Kazakhstan sample had mean scores that increased with age in a linear fashion. However, the difference between the high and low mean scores was not significant ($p = 0.4800$). The Russia sample had mean scores that decreased with age in a linear fashion. The difference between the high and low mean scores was significant ($p < 0.0001$), indicating older people tend to be significantly more opposed to tax evasion than younger people.

Table 4

Justifiability of Tax Evasion (Age)

	Azerbaijan	Georgia	Kazakhstan	Russia	Turkey
Up to 29					
Mean	3.03	2.18	2.88	4.34	1.68
Std. Dev.	2.77	2.20	2.43	2.99	1.65
n	445	461	283	883	702
30-49					
Mean	3.11	2.27	2.94	4.05	1.71
Std. Dev.	2.76	2.22	2.51	2.91	1.65
n	715	771	575	1233	1078
50+					
Mean	2.80	2.22	3.02	3.14	1.66
Std. Dev.	2.54	2.04	2.55	2.59	1.61
n	567	958	354	1397	614

Taxing the Rich and Subsidizing the Poor

The issue of taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor has several facets worth exploring. One might apply cold, hard economic analysis. If one does that, one relationship that comes to mind is that if you tax something you will get less of it, and if you subsidize something you will get more of it. Thus, if you tax the rich, you will have fewer rich, not only because the government confiscates a portion of their wealth, but also because it takes away their incentive to create more wealth. Likewise, if you subsidize the poor, you will get more poor people because it takes away their incentive to work and get out of poverty.

Another view is that there is a social, moral or religious obligation to help the poor, and those who are rich are the people who are best able to help. A related question is who should provide this help, and should it be left to private individuals, nonprofit organizations or government? But the issue is more complicated than that. The concept of charity includes the premise that any charitable contribution is voluntary and freely given. One form of voluntary assistance is the case where individuals give directly to those in need. Another form of voluntary assistance is the case where individuals donate to a nonprofit organization, which then uses the proceeds to distribute to those who are less fortunate.

The third option is to assign this task to the government. In this case, the proceeds raised are not the result of charity because they are not voluntary contributions.

They are coerced. Or are they? Some philosophers take the position that there is a social contract [64; 65], and that the tax funds raised for any governmental purpose are raised by the consent of the people. In other words, the people have consented to be taxed and, in a democracy, the government representatives are doing the will of the people. If the government decides to use some of the tax funds collected to distribute to the poor, they do it with the consent of the taxpayers. One criticism of this line of reasoning is that many (perhaps most) taxpayers have not given their consent [66]. In a democracy, the government officials who are elected are performing tasks that perhaps only 50.1 percent of those who voted approve. The remaining 49.9 percent of those who voted might very easily disapprove of using their tax money to subsidize the poor. And what about those who did not vote? They still must pay taxes, and their views may not be reflected by the government that has been elected by others.

This argument assumes that those who are elected are actually doing things that have the approval of more than half of the population, but that may not be the case in fact. Governments often do things that do not have majority approval. Many voters and nonvoters do not even know how the government is spending their money. Thus, any approval they might have given is at least partially given out of ignorance.

That being the case, the World Values Survey [61] has provided data on how popular the view is that an essential function of government is to tax the rich and subsidize the poor. This view is a close cousin to the theory of progressive taxation, a theory that has been criticized [66]. The theory and morality of redistribution of wealth has also been criticized [67]. A few studies have examined this issue. McGee and Yoon examined the views in Korea [51]. McGee, Yoon and Liu [60] conducted a similar study of German opinion. McGee, Benk and Yüzbaşı [46; 47] did a comparative study of Christian and Muslim views on the issue. The common feature of these studies was that there is a certain amount of support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor, and that demographic variables such as gender, age and religion sometimes make a difference.

To what extent do the people in the selected five Euro-Asian countries agree with this policy? The results are given below. The survey instrument included a 10-point Likert Scale where 1 = It is against democracy (Not an essential characteristic of democracy) and 10 = An essential characteristic of democracy. The means, standard deviations and sample size (n) for each country are given in Table 5.

Overall

Table 5

Overall Ranking. Taxing the Rich and Subsidizing the Poor
(1 = not an essential characteristic of democracy;
10 = An essential characteristic of democracy)

Rank	Country	Mean	Std. Dev.	n
1	Turkey	5.11	3.32	1974
2	Georgia	5.84	2.83	2336
3	Kazakhstan	6.17	3.36	1633
4	Azerbaijan	6.71	2.86	1192
5	Russia	7.44	2.66	3484

The Russian sample had the strongest support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor, in the sense that they believed doing so was an essential characteristic of democracy. The Georgian sample showed the least support for this position. However, all five countries showed strong support for the view that an essential characteristic of democracy is to tax the rich and subsidize the poor. The relative p-value tests of significance are shown in Table 6. All differences in mean score are significant.

Table 6

Taxing the Rich and Subsidizing the Poor. Tests of Significance
(Significant if $p < 0.05$)

	Turkey	Azerbaijan	Kazakhstan	Russia
Georgia	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Turkey		0.0012	<0.0001	<0.0001
Azerbaijan			<0.0001	<0.0001
Kazakhstan				<0.0001

Gender

Table 7 shows the gender views. Male and female views did not differ significantly for the Azerbaijan, Russia and Turkey samples. Georgian men showed significantly stronger support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor than did the women, although most showed strong support, as evidenced by the mean scores. Kazak women showed significantly stronger support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor than did Kazak men, although both showed strong support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor.

Table 7

Taxing the Rich and Subsidizing the Poor (Gender Differences)

	Male			Female			p-value
	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	
Azerbaijan	6.29	3.33	840	6.05	3.40	793	0.1501
Georgia	5.29	3.45	932	4.94	3.20	1042	0.0200
Kazakhstan	6.50	2.84	546	6.89	2.85	646	0.0185
Russia	7.38	2.64	1580	7.49	2.68	1904	0.2241
Turkey	5.81	2.88	1177	5.86	2.77	1159	0.6689

Age

Comparisons were also made by age. Table 8 shows the statistics for each country. Several different relationships could be seen. Support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor declined with age for the Azerbaijan sample. Support increased for the Georgia, Russia and Turkey samples. The relationship between age and support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor was curvilinear for the Kazakhstan sample. Support decreased, then increased. The difference between the high and low mean scores were significant for Georgia ($p = 0.0219$), Kazakhstan ($p = 0.0050$) and Russia ($p < 0.0001$). The difference between the high and low mean score was not significant for Azerbaijan ($p = 0.2900$) and Turkey ($p = 0.6162$).

Table 8

Taxing the Rich and Subsidizing the Poor (Age)

	Azerbaijan	Georgia	Kazakhstan	Russia	Turkey
Up to 29					
Mean	6.31	4.80	6.73	6.86	5.78
Std. Dev.	3.32	3.28	2.89	2.66	2.79
n	420	436	281	866	679
30-49					
Mean	6.22	5.13	6.50	7.37	5.86
Std. Dev.	3.32	3.25	2.94	2.73	2.80
n	675	694	558	1235	1055
50+					
Mean	6.02	5.25	7.03	7.87	5.86
Std. Dev.	3.45	3.40	2.66	2.52	2.90
n	537	843	353	1383	601

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study explored two public finance questions – when is tax evasion justifiable, and whether it is a legitimate function of government to tax the rich and subsidize the poor. We were not able to answer these questions, of course. That was not the purpose of this essay. The goal was to obtain the views of the people in the five Euro-Asian countries in order to learn how they thought about these two issues. That goal was achieved.

Although all five countries showed strong opposition to tax evasion, some countries showed more resistance to it than others. Turkey was by far the country most opposed to tax evasion, while Russia showed the least resistance, which is in keeping with other studies [69; 70]. The gender portion of the study was interesting. Other studies [48; 71] had found two basic patterns. Either women were significantly more opposed to tax evasion than men or men and women were equally opposed to tax evasion. A very small minority of studies found men to be more significantly opposed to tax evasion [72; 73]. In the present study, all five countries had populations where men and women were equally opposed to tax evasion.

An examination of the age variable also produced some interesting results. Most studies found that opposition to tax evasion increased with age [74; 75], but this study found that to be the case for only one country – Russia.

The question about taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor produced some ground-breaking results, since not much empirical research has been done on this issue. Overall, support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor was strong. Men and women had similar opinions about this issue in Azerbaijan, Russia and Turkey; Georgian men showed significantly stronger support for this policy than did Georgian women. In Kazakhstan the women were significantly more in support of the policy than the men. Thus, three different patterns emerged out of a five-country sample. Obviously, more research needs to be done on this issue. Age was not a significant demographic variable for Azerbaijan and Turkey. Support for taxing the rich and subsidizing the poor increased significantly with age for Georgia, Kazakhstan and Russia.

One criticism that could be made of the World Values Survey data is that no reasons were given as to why the respondents answered the way they did. That is understandable, given the fact that the survey instrument used consisted of hundreds of questions. Requiring respondents to give reasons for each answer would have been overly burdensome. Future studies could remedy this deficiency by probing

for the rationale given be respondents for their answers. Such studies would have to be smaller in scope, and with fewer survey questions. Some studies have been done using this approach, but more studies are needed [76].

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The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Viktor V. Zinchenko, Institute of the Society of Kyiv University named after Boris Grinchenko (Ukraine)